

PHYSICAL FORCES AWARE AGING SIMULATION ON CULTURAL HERITAGE ARTIFACTS

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ABSTRACT

Cultural heritage objects tend to change in appearance over time due to weathering phenomena and physical force effects, such as gravity or wind. Simulating such phenomena can be a useful guide for conservators and restorers. In this direction, the current paper proposes an aging simulation method which models the impact of physical forces using a particle-based approach. The proposed simulation method enhances the realism of the aging simulation through the creation of realistically shaped geometry regions for the decay formation under the effect of physical forces. Particularly, the case of gravitational accelerations effect was examined. The method is general and its application can be extended to different kinds of materials and weathering phenomena. A metallic sculpture has been used as a case study and the qualitative results presented in each intermediate processing step, demonstrate the overall functionality and the promising potential of the suggested approach in comparison with other existing methods and the decayed appearance of cultural heritage objects in their natural environment.

Index Terms — aging simulation, cultural heritage, environmental forces, particle-based simulation, 3D representation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The simulation of weathering effects on cultural heritage (CH) artifacts has long been a field of systematic research in an interdisciplinary domain closely related to material science, biology and archaeology. Modelling weathering phenomena effects often requires collaboration of multi-specialization professionals and can be a laborious work according to the level of realism and connection with the underlying weathering mechanisms that is intended to achieve. The steadfast demand on increased realism and reflection of the intrinsic mechanisms causing the aging effects on CH assets is regularly expressed by relevant professionals, scholars and organizations, such as conservators or film production organizations. In the last decades, various significant works have been done towards this direction. Thus, there are various state-of-the-art aging simulation methods focusing on modelling particular weathering phenomena effects either in high or low level detail and others that are more general and consider various weathering phenomena simultaneously.

In this paper we propose a method for simulating spatio-temporally the effect of external environmental forces, such as gravity or wind, on aging effects taking place on CH objects. The weathering phenomena that could be influenced by such forces are those that involve chemical processes. The distribution of the reactants along the surface of the artworks and consequently, the final shape of the decay region formed could be defined under the effect of the environmental forces. There is a gap in the existing state-of-the-art simulation methods towards this direction, apart from few

works, where such effects have been considered during the decay formation process, as presented in Section 2. The proposed simulation method uses 3D textured mesh models of CH artworks as reference and a particle-based aging simulation method as basis.

The paper is organized as follows: a review of the related work is presented in Section 2; the proposed aging simulation approach is introduced in Section 3, while in Section 4 the experimental results of the proposed method are given. Finally, we draw the main conclusions of our work in Section 5.

2. RELATED WORK

Over the last decades several papers in computer graphics have proposed methodologies to simulate aging phenomena on CH items with the goal being to provide insight into the life-cycle of these items. The entire range of weathering effects and materials is covered more or less by existing state-of-the-art varying in the level of realism they achieve, the accuracy and the complexity of the algorithms. A typical example for the modelling of patina formation effect and an appearance rendering based on Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) functions is [1], while a mathematical model of copper corrosion is also given by [2]. Modeling of time-variant materials appearance through appearance manifolds is achieved in [3]. A simulation method of fruit senescence and appearance rendering based on distribution maps is proposed in [4].

A particle-based simulation method that could cover various cases of weathering phenomena and that proposes a realistic rendering method is [5]. J.T.Kider [6] combines the proposed method [4] for the simulation of fruit senescence and the particle-based simulation method of [5] to simulate weathering effects of multiple phenomena that may occur simultaneously, as well. He also provides a rendering routine based on reaction-diffusion texture synthesis, as proposed in [7]. Finally, a particle-based method for aging simulation on CH objects that models the decay diffusion using Gaussian-like regions with Gaussian distribution was proposed in [8]. We extend this work by incorporating cardioid-like decay regions with Gaussian distribution for more realistic decay diffusion. On the whole, a detailed overview of the above methods and more related ones can be found in [9].

3. SPATIO-TEMPORAL AGING SIMULATION METHOD

The particle-based aging simulation method used in this work is based on the proposed framework of J.T.Kider [6]. The input of the simulation method is a replica of an artwork in the form of a 3D mesh model along with its texture. The simulation of an artwork's aging is performed in aging cycles. In each aging cycle special aging particles, called μ -tons, regulate the aging processes; they are emitted and propagated in the scene. As μ -tons intersect with the mesh of an object they leave decay on the intersecting faces of the mesh. After each aging cycle new decay colonies

are created with each new collision and the old ones are diffused under the effect of gravity following a Gaussian-like model and finally, decay is visualized in an artwork's surface. An overview of the entire workflow is illustrated in Figure 1. The following subsections describe in greater detail the components of the proposed framework elaborating on their algorithmic modules.

Figure 1: Aging simulation method overview of a digitized artwork.

3.1. The μ -ton particles

The core of the aging mechanism consists of the *emitter μ -tons*, which have an initial amount of energy and generate new *decay μ -tons* distributing among them their energy. The *decay μ -tons* are the decay carriers. Decay in most materials is the result of a chemical process, which normally needs some "nutrients" to take place. Thus, decay μ -tons are technically the "nutrients" carriers that activate the chemical processes of the decay. The energy that each decay μ -ton possesses regulates the "nutrients" deposits. Decay μ -tons propagate through the scene and lose a portion of their energy after each collision with the object's mesh.

(a) Bronze copy of San Giorgio statue (Donatello 1415).

(b) 3D digitised model of San Giorgio statue with an elliptic cone spot source placed on top of the region of highest humidity concentration.

Figure 2: The reference artwork sample used in the validation of the proposed aging simulation of CH objects.

3.2. The μ -ton emission, propagation & intersection

The emitter μ -tons are arranged on sources of various geometry. The geometry of the source regulates the distribution of decay μ -tons in the scene. An elliptic cone spot source was used for this

work, that generates decay μ -tons along random rays within the cone. Emitter μ -tons generate new decay μ -tons, as long as they have enough energy left and they also define decay μ -tons' initial velocity. The decay μ -tons propagate in the scene in time-steps and their collisions with the surfaces form colonies of decay. The framework implements appropriate responses to the collisions; the decay μ -tons reflect on the surfaces or settle, when their energy is not enough for another intersection. The decay is appropriately updated after each collision. Figure 2b depicts the μ -ton framework's implementation with an elliptic cone spot source placed on top of a 3D digitised object and generating new decay μ -tons.

3.3. Decay Diffusion

"Nutrients" are deposited on the surface of the artwork after each collision of decay μ -tons with the surface of the mesh. For example, patina formation is mainly due to water concentration on artworks surface [2]. This water under the effect of gravity moves in flows downward following the geometry of the object. Patina is formed and degrades along the water flows that become narrower with the distance from the concentrated water. As patina is formed, water is consumed and smaller amounts of it are left to continue flowing downwards.

Thus, considering the effect of gravity on the formation of the "nutrients" flows, this method proposes the modelling of the decay regions formation as a cardioid aligned with the gravity direction. The cardioid's tail models the narrowing of the "nutrients" flows. Within the cardioid regions the distribution of the "nutrients" follow a Gaussian distribution with the axis of greatest standard deviation aligned with the gravity direction. After each aging cycle, the cardioid gets bigger so that its tail becomes longer to simulate the "nutrients" flow towards the gravitational acceleration, and the greatest standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution increases as more water and hence patina, distributes along the gravity direction.

The cardioid-parametric Gaussian function is:

$$F(x, y, \phi, t, n, d, g) = m \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{(x(\phi)-x_0)^2}{2\sigma_x^2(t, n, d, g)} + \frac{(y(\phi)-y_0)^2}{2\sigma_y^2(n, d)}\right)}. \quad (1)$$

The center of the distribution (x_0, y_0) is the intersection point of the decay μ -ton and its axis is the decay μ -ton's incidence direction. The Gaussian-like region's standard deviations, σ_x, σ_y increase proportionately to the number of decay μ -tons having fallen onto the same intersection point, n , and inversely proportionately to the deviation of the axis direction from the meshes normal vectors direction at that point, d . Additionally, σ_x increases with time, t , assuming that axis-x aligns with gravity and is proportional to the gravitational acceleration g .

The parametric representation of the cardioid-like regions is given by the following equations:

$$x(\phi) = 2 \cdot \alpha(t, n, d, g) \cdot (1 - \cos \phi) \cdot \cos \phi \quad (2)$$

$$y(\phi) = 2 \cdot \frac{\alpha(t, n, d, g)}{\beta} \cdot (1 - \cos \phi) \cdot \sin \phi \quad (3)$$

where $\beta > 1$ is constant, $\phi \in \{0, 2\pi\}$. α increases with time, t , is proportional to the number of decay μ -tons having fallen onto the same intersection point, n and the gravitational acceleration g and inversely proportionately to the deviation of the axis direction from the meshes normal vectors direction at that point, d . Figure 3 presents cardioid-parametric Gaussian distributions for various parameters α and σ_x .

Figure 3: Different parameters of cardioid-parametric Gaussian distributions.

Figure 4: Decayed appearance rendering.

3.4. Rendering

The decay rendering is based on the texture mapping and texture blending. The combination of the cultural object’s texture with a texture of the undergoing decay (e.g. patina) is the result of linear interpolation of object’s texture color to_i and decay’s texture color td_i of the i -th pixel using a to weight between them. Both textures must have the same size.

$$c_i = to_i * (1 - a) + td_i * a \quad (4)$$

The $a \in [0, 1]$ interpolation factor indicates the concentration of decay on the object’s regions. A 2D decay concentration map is formed after each aging cycle and updates the decay concentration factors, which are used for the rendering. Decay concentration factors in our implementation are retrieved from the 3D Gaussian ($m = 1$) for the vertices of the object’s mesh within the cardioid-like region. Figure 4 presents the decayed appearance rendering process followed by our implementation.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The evaluation and validation of the proposed method for aging simulation was performed on a metallic sculpture with a real case of patina formation. Specifically, the reference artwork sample used (Figure 2a) is a $200 \times 50cm$ bronze copy of a marble sculpture depicting San Giorgio and made by Donatello in 1415. The external environmental conditions as presented in [2] have resulted

in the formation of patina mainly along the shield of the statue starting from the contact area of the hand with the shield on the top basis of the shield (Figure 5a). The basis of the shield concentrates water from the rain or the existing atmospheric humidity.

Figure 5 presents the result of the patina formation simulation. The μ -ton framework was used with an elliptical cone spot source placed on top of the shield’s top basis, since this is an area of high humidity concentration in reality. For the evaluation of the method three methods were considered; The method that forms decay in Gaussian-like regions [8], the method presented in this paper that forms decay in cardioid-like regions considering the effect of gravity and the reaction-diffusion method proposed by [4]. The simulations were run for about 1000, 3000 and 2500 ageing cycles, respectively. The parameters for the cardioid-like regions were $\alpha = 1.3$ and $\beta = 2$.

In the case of cardioid shaped decay regions (Figure 5c), patina is formed in flows that get narrower as they expand downwards along the shield of the statue simulating in a more realistic way the patina formation in comparison to the actual patina formation, as depicted for example in Figure 5a. The other methods (Figures 5b and 5d) tend to form circular decay regions that they do not seem to have a common ”spring”. That has to do with the fact that method [8] diffuses decay in Gaussian-like regions around the decay μ -tons intersections with the objects, while the reaction-diffusion method diffuses decay radially, not considering gravity direction.

(a) San Giorgio bronze statue in its natural environment with the region of high humidity concentration designated by a red cycle.

(b) Patina simulation within Gaussian-like decay regions.

(c) Patina simulation within cardioid-like decay regions.

(d) Patina simulation using the reaction-diffusion method.

Figure 5: Patina formation simulation according to a real case.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper describes a method for the simulation of degradation phenomena on their surface of CH objects caused by force effects (e.g. gravity, wind) using a particle-based approach. In the presented method, an aging simulation engine implementing the μ -ton framework simulates the weathering processes on the artworks. A Gaussian-based approach is adopted to represent the decay regions' forming and the decay expansion within cardioid regions aligned with the direction of the acting forces. The appearance rendering of the decayed artwork's model based on texture mapping and blending is the last step that results in a realistic representation of the proposed method in comparison with the Gaussian-like shaped decay regions, the reaction-diffusion approach and the current appearance of a copper sculpture in its natural environment is presented.

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